

The FTIR Spectra of Raw Magnesite and Sintered Magnesite

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ABSTRACT

Magnesite is a magnesium carbonate mineral because of its thermal stability and inertness. All the three grades of magnesite both in raw and sintered forms have vast applications. The FTIR spectra of raw magnesite and sintered magnesite samples have been recorded in the mid - infrared region of 4000-450 cm⁻¹. In general, vibrational spectroscopy detections can qualitatively and quantitatively distinguish the spectral assignment of specific bands between corresponding bonds and functional groups, as also the observation of spectral profiles can be used to define and differentiate the magnesite. The present work is aimed to make an investigation magnesite

Keywords: *Magnesite, FTIR*

INTRODUCTION

Magnesium is one of most widely distributed elements in the earth crust of which it constitute nearly 2.7 percent and so occupies the sixth place on list (1) magnesium carbonate occurs in nature as magnesite and in association with calcium carbonate as dolomite. The majorly of magnesium oxide produced today is obtained from the processing of naturally occurring minerals such as magnesite (magnesium carbonate) (2). Large Mineral deposits of magnesia are in Austria, Brazil, Canada, China, Common wealth of Independent States, former Czechoslovakia, Greece, Turkey, North Korea, former Yugoslavia and the US . The commercial production of magnesia in India was started during the World War I, when imports of magnesium chloride was ceased and in indigenous resources must be developed to meet the needs of industry (4). The bitterns from marine salt works provided a convenient

source material for magnesium chloride and the pioneer magnesia works limited Kraalhead, started production in 1916.

The Chemical name of magnesite is magnesium carbonate (MgCO₃) (i.e) Magnesite is a carbonate of magnesium. When pure, it contains 52.4 % carbon di-oxide (CO₂) and 47.6% magnesium oxide (MgO) (3). The magnesium and calcium bearing carbonates represent an important mineral group which is mined extensively. It is usually white, but it may be light to dark brown if iron bearing. Magnesite is an important industrial mineral. Various types of magnesite are produced by different thermal treatments and it is used in the production of calcined, dead- burned . Magnesite is converted to calcined magnesite when it heated between 700 °C and 1000 °C temperatures. Calcined magnesite is used in the manufacture of paints, paper, plastic, rubber, oil, pharmaceutical, fertilizer, animal feed, building materials and as a fire retardant. If calcined Magnesite is heated to 1500 °C to 1800 °C, it will convert to dead- burned magnesite which is known as sintered magnesite and it is used predominantly for refractory bricks are widely used in many industrial sectors e.g. pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries, paint formulations and bulk applications including concrete and magnesia (MgO) production. There have been a considerable number of studies suggesting that magnesite should be considered when evaluating the role of carbon in the earth's mantle. Magnesite is indeed a very good candidate for hosting oxidized carbon in the mantle, since experiments or calculations indicate that magnesite is, among all carbonates the most stable at

high pressure and high temperature (6-11). Numerous experiments have been dedicated to determine the compression properties of magnesite, as these govern to some extent to its stability versus the composition into a mixture of oxides MgO and CO₂. Recently the high-pressure behaviour of magnesite has been studied with angle dispersive X-ray diffraction by Fiquet et al and Reynard et al (12-15). Ross et al carried out even the structural refinement of magnesite at high pressure in 1997(16). Though many research works were carried out in magnesite at high pressure not much work was reported at high temperature. Here an attempt is made to study the behaviour of the ceramic (MgO) at different temperatures, using infra red.

Experimental and Methods:

FT- IR Spectral Analysis

Natural samples of Raw Magnesite, LBM, HBM and different grades of DBM have been procured from TANMAG (Tamil Nadu Magnesite Limited), Salem, India. The FTIR spectra were recorded in the range 4000-400 cm⁻¹ using Bruker IFS 66V FTIR spectrophotometer at SAIF, IIT, Chennai, India. Since the samples were not soluble in solvent and also the preparation of the film was very difficult, the IR spectra were recorded by the use of KBr pellet method. .

Result and discussion

Since the samples were not soluble in solvent and also the preparation of the film was very difficult, the IR spectra were recorded by the use of KBr pellet method. The FTIR spectra of the raw magnesite and the sintered magnesite samples are presented in Figs. 1 Different grades of DBM Spectra are presented in Figs..2 Recently the IR spectra have been utilized as an analytical tool by chemists and mineralogists. Many researchers collected the characteristic IR spectra of minerals and rocks for identification of known minerals and mixtures (20-24). IR technique was also applied to characterise the water and hydroxyl ions in the basic magnesium carbonate minerals by White(25). The thermal behaviour of calcite, kalonite and dolomite in ceramics were reported recently (26-28). The analysis of magnesite samples under the spectral investigation show interesting relationship with its mechanical and electrical properties. The infrared spectrum of raw magnesite shows a very strong broad band at 1446

cm⁻¹ due to the asymmetric C-O stretching vibrations and it is in good agreement with the literature value (29). This band is identified by laitha et al (30) at 1450 cm⁻¹ in apatites sample to confirm the presence of CO₃ ion. As the sintering process takes place, this band slightly shifts to 1455 cm⁻¹ with less absorbance. In DBM it completely disappears to show the absence of CO₃ ion.

Another intense band at 856 cm⁻¹ is characteristic of the CO₃ asymmetric deformation as expected. This band appears with less intensity in LBM and disappears in both DBM. Similarly the weak bands at 1080 cm⁻¹ and 680 cm⁻¹ may be due to the C-O symmetric and CO₃ symmetric deformation vibration. Following the frequency assignment done by Nakamoto (29), the bands at 1446 cm⁻¹, 856 cm⁻¹, 1080 cm⁻¹ and 680 cm⁻¹ are confirmed as fundamental modes of CO₃ ion present in MgCO₃. These four bands that are due to the CO₃ ion present in the raw magnesite (MgCO₃) sample disappear one by one in sintered magnesite sample to prove that the CO₂ gas is expelled completely in the process of calcination at high temperature (1750°C). The frequency interpretation is tabulated for raw in table 1 and sintered magnesites in Table.2. The values within the bracket gives the corresponding absorbance. The strong band near 887 cm⁻¹ is due to the Mg-O stretching vibration (29) and this is active in all grades of DBM. The observed fundamentals along with their assignments for different grades of DBM are presented in Table 3.3. Values of the absorbance of the characteristic bands corresponding to the components present are given within the parenthesis in the table. The spectra of different grades of DBM give rise to more or less same infrared characteristic bands since there is a very small variation in the percentage of components present in it. Comparing the percentage of MgO with other components of DBM it is very high and varies between 72% and 89% and thus leads to a variation of absorbance in the range 0.33% to 0.70%. The second major contribution in DBM is due to SiO₂ and shows absorbance up to 0.59%.

The IR absorbance for SiO, Si₂O₂ molecules are observed at 1224 cm⁻¹ (SiO), 805 cm⁻¹, 766 cm⁻¹ (Si₂O₂), 973 cm⁻¹, 632 cm⁻¹, 312 cm⁻¹ (Si₃O₂) by Ogden and Anderson (31). The peaks around 839 cm⁻¹, 987 cm⁻¹ and 471 cm⁻¹ are invariably present in all the grades of DBM, caused by a symmetrical stretching (32,33), asymmetric stretching (34,35) and bending vibrations (36,37) of Si-O group confirms its

presence. Yousuf (38) ascribes the stretching vibrations of Al-O around 1000 cm^{-1} and the same is identified at 987 cm^{-1} in DBM grade samples and gives more or less the same value of absorbance. The stretching vibrations of Ca-O occur normally at 650 cm^{-1} (39) and here it is observed around 614 cm^{-1} . The absorbance of this peak is very small compared to the other impurities like Al_2O_3 value. The strong band near 887 cm^{-1} is due to the Mg-O stretching vibration (29) and this is active in all grades of DBM. The observed fundamentals along with their assignments for different grades of DBM are presented in Table 3.2

Table 1 FTIR spectral analysis on raw magnesite different Grades

Band assignments	Grade 1 Wave number cm^{-1}	Grade 1 Wave number cm^{-1}	Grade 1 Wave number cm^{-1}
Mg-O	885	885	885
SiO_2 Asymmetric Stg	1020	1020	1020
Asymmetric . CO stg	1446	1446	1446
Asymmetric CO stg	1080	1080	1080
Asymmetric CO_3 def	856	856	856
symmetric CO_3 def	680	680	680

Fig 1 FTIR raw magnesite

Table 2 FTIR spectral analysis on Sintering magnesite different Grade

Band assignments	Wave number cm^{-1}	Wave number cm^{-1}	Wave number cm^{-1}
Mg-O	887	886	887
SiO_2 Asymmetric Stg	1017	1018	1017
Asymmetric CO stg	-	-	-
Asymmetric CO stg	-	-	-
Asymmetric CO_3 def	-	-	-
symmetric CO_3 def			-

Fig 2 FTIR DBM magnesit

Conclusions

The FTIR measurement is used to analyze the samples of magnesite. The FTIR technique is used to identify the characteristic bands of Silicate, aluminium, iron, present in the mineral, and a spectral analysis is also carried by FTIR. It is observed that the magnesite is more stable and has high mechanical strength, because of the presence of silica. The spectroscopic instrumentation techniques are used to conclude out of the three grades. They are in good agreement with the FTIR techniques and dielectric measurement results.

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